

Analysis of Imaging Media

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Annotation: *In this article, information is given about the existence of specific visual and expressive means of the pencil drawing in Fine Art, and the fact that the depiction requires the correct and appropriate use of lines. Studying and understanding the laws of harmony directs the work of artists to create new works that correspond to the objective laws of perception and harmony of nature.*

Key words: *pencil drawing, Fine Art, light and shadow, analytical thinking, complex subject, imaging media.*

Introduction: It is important to understand the expressive language of visual arts and to use it in practice. Concepts of composition, line, spot, color, size, shape, space, texture, analysis of the works of well-known great artists are taken as an expressive language of visual art and they are carried out through departments of painting, graphics, sculpture, and art history. Lines, dashes, contours, colors, and black-and-white spots are used as expressive means of pen drawing. In nature, every item and thing has its own color. In these colors, light shades occupy a very large place. In fine art, the pencil drawing type also has its own visual and expressive tools. In particular, depiction requires correct and appropriate use of lines. According to their shape, they are straight, oblique, arc-shaped, rounded, and mixed.

They are applied depending on the shape and structural structure of the item being described. For example, it is recommended to use arc-shaped lines (strokes) to describe the size of the rain-shadow part of the candle, that is, different types of strokes are used in different places to reveal the shape, size and character of the picture. The technique of working with dreams on paper can also be used in order to increase the expressive potential of pencil works. Slanted strokes are used as an expressive tool when creating a pencil drawing. Dots are also used as a visual and expressive tool in pencil works.

Main part: The line is the main image tool in painting, and its character serves as a certain working tool or tool for the artist. An artist's true performance of this or that task depends on the style of drawing and the pressure applied to the paper surface. The line in the picture can be free and different: sometimes strong, primary and black, sometimes light, a little unknown. The hard pressed line serves as a step to darken the shadow parts of the object. Such lines are not used to express the image of a body in a distance based on perspective. Such a line can be used to make decorative images. Lines are optical phenomena that allow the artist to direct the viewer's eye. The optical illusion of line exists in nature, and elements of visual art can be separated to create this illusion. The viewer unconsciously reads next to a continuous arrangement of elements and subject matter at different distances. Such elements can be used dramatically in the composition of the image. It can literally be towing lines, such as telephone and electrical cables, or even a boat. Stripes can result from different color boundaries or contrast, or from the sequence of individual elements. A dash is a relatively short line. With more in one place and less in another, they create different colors in the picture. Drawing different numbers of lines on the parts allows you to show the size and shape of the depicted object.

A flat layer is created using strokes of the same spacing and tone, for example, along the diagonal of a square. To achieve a darker shade, the second layer is covered in the other direction over the first

layer. Light to dark and dark to light transitions can be done in two ways: by shading on different color boundaries, or by continuously varying pen pressure and stroke spacing.

The character of the line work is compatible with the shape of the product, the size of the shape is correctly represented in the picture, and it ensures that the structure of the product is realistic. On the other hand, a wrongly executed line drawing is distinguished by its falsification and spoils it. The appearance of a figure depends not only on the angle from which it is viewed, but also on the state of light and tone of the body, which can change the perception of the body. But in the sculptural type of visual art, the sculptor and painter never pay attention to these situations, because he works with form in his creation. At times, he may not notice or see small, inconspicuous parts of the model.

In this regard, the artist should learn from the sculptor. It is not enough for an artist to see a body, he must also know and feel that body. While working on the picture, the artist should act as if he were creating a sculpture in his imagination.

In order to learn the volume-realistic drawing technique, it is necessary to study the general laws of perception of a volume (three-dimensional) object in space (space). Two factors have a decisive influence on perception: the distance from the viewer to the picture and the aerial layer, in other words, linear and aerial perspective.

Color consists of light and shadow. Only the highlighted object will be visible. Rays reflecting from different objects and at different speeds fall on the retina, and all the rays combine to form a light and a shadow. Light and shade reflex (an involuntary reaction of a living organism in response to external influences) from the following elements: its own shadow, half-tone, light and shadow, are of great importance in creating a form. Here we should also add drop shadows and deep shadows, although these types of shadows do not directly participate in the formation of the size of the object. Light and shadow are two generalized parts of a real image image.

Conclusion: In order to correctly determine the proportions of the parts of the object, drawing, in addition to knowledge, must have a sense of proportion. A sense of proportion means a good eye, and the eye usually develops through long practice in drawing from nature. It is necessary to develop analytical thinking by opening the eyes. The mistake of relying on the eye alone can lead to repetition. Such an approach is unacceptable, especially when drawing complex subject shapes such as the human head. There are many examples of students relying on their eyes, guessing, and copying everything they see.

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